

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Organizational change and employees' work life balance in ABC semiconductor company

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Abstract

This article investigated the link between organizational change and employee work-life balance at ABC Semiconductor, a prominent company in the Biñan, Laguna Philippines. It aimed to analyze the change's impact and identify influencing factors. Quantitative methods gathered data via surveys, offering statistical insights. The findings revealed a multifaceted relationship between change and work-life balance. Key factors like communication quality, employee participation, top management attitude, and supervisor support were found to impact employee well-being through stress, self, time, and change management during transitions. An action plan for improving work-life balance amidst change was proposed.

Keywords Organizational change; Work-life balance; Employee well-being; Semiconductor

1. Introduction

This study used the Readiness for Change model. Readiness for change is seen as one of the key success factors when organizations implement changes measuring the; quality of change communication, participation, attitude of top management and support by supervisor within the organization, Mladenova [58]. This model was used as independent variable.

For the dependent variable, this research adopted the work-life balance individual approach model which will focus; stress management, self-management, time management and change management by Abiog[1].

Figure 1 shows the paradigm of the study using the organizational change indicators and work-life balance manifestation level. This figure represents the research paradigm for the proposed study. The independent variable; Organizational Change Manifestation in ABC Semiconductor Company which consist of four components—Quality of Change Communication, Participation taken, Attitude of top management, Support by Supervisor. The dependent variable, Work-Life Balance Manifestation in ABC Semiconductor Company which consist of four components—Stress Management, Self-Management, Time Management, Change Management. This study assessed the organizational change from the viewpoint of the Rank and File Employees that would lead to identifying areas of improvement in resources management and operational guidelines on post pandemic area.

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Figure 1 Research Paradigm

The research further sought to answer the following questions:

- What is the level of manifestation of organizational change as to process of change in ABC Semiconductor Company as assessed by rank-and-file employees in terms of:
 - Quality of Change Communication;
 - Participation Taken;
 - Attitude of Top Management; and
 - Support by Supervisor?
- What is level of manifestation of employee’s work-life balance level in ABC Semiconductor Company in terms of:
 - Stress Management;
 - Self-Management;
 - Time Management; and
 - Change Management?
- Is there any significant relationship between level of manifestation of organizational change and the level manifestation of employees’ work-life balance in ABC Semiconductor Company?
- Based on the findings of the study, what action plan may be proposed?

Based on the data gathered and after careful and thorough analysis of the investigation, the following are the findings of the study in summarized form.

- Level of Manifestation of Organizational Change as to Process Change in ABC Semiconductor Company as assessed by Rank-and-File Employees in terms of:
 - Quality of Change Communication
- It had a general assessment of 2.97 interpreted as Manifested.
 - Participation Taken
- It had a general assessment 2.98 interpreted as Manifested.
 - Attitude of Top Management
- It had a general assessment of 3.11 interpreted as Manifested.
 - Support by the Supervisor
- It had a general assessment of 2.88 interpreted as Manifested.
- Level of Manifestation of Employees’ Work-Life Balance level in ABC Semiconductor Company in terms of:
 - Stress Management
- It had a general assessment of 2.77 interpreted as Manifested.
 - Self-Management
- It had a general assessment of 2.89 interpreted as Manifested.
 - Time Management
- It had a general assessment of 2.92 interpreted as Manifested.
 - Change Management
- It had a general assessment of 3.00 interpreted as Manifested.

1.1. Test of Significant Relationship between Level of Manifestation of Organizational Change and the Level of Manifestation of Employees' Work-Life Balance in ABC Semiconductor Company:

- In terms of Quality of Change Communication, it had a significant relationship with stress management, self-management, time management, and change management. The computed probability values (.000) were lesser than the level of significant ($P < 0.05$); thus, rejecting the null hypothesis.
- In terms of Participation Taken, it had a significant relationship with stress management, self-management, time management, and change management. The computed probability values (.000) were lesser than the level of significant ($P < 0.05$); thus, rejecting the null hypothesis.
- In terms of Attitude of Top Management, it had no significant relationship with any aspect of work-life balance. The computed probability values of .471, .226, .485, and .661 were all higher than the level of significance, indicating that the null hypothesis was accepted.
- In terms of Support by the Supervisor, it had a significant relationship with stress management, self-management, time management, and change management. The computed probability values (.000) were lesser than the level of significant ($P < 0.05$); thus, rejecting the null hypothesis.

1.2. The Proposed Action Plan

The study proposed an action plan to improve the level of work-life balance due to organizational change. It is a comprehensive plan to assess and address the impact of organizational change on rank-and-file employees. It emphasizes effective communication, training, support, stress management, and awareness-building programs. By implementing these strategies and monitoring the success indicators, the organization can strive to ensure a smoother transition and a positive experience for its employees during the change process.

1.3. Conclusions

Based on the results of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

- That good communication is crucial for organizational change. It ensures relevant information is shared with stakeholders, including reasons, outcomes, and steps. When employees actively participate in change, they develop ownership and commitment. The attitude of top management is crucial for successful organizational change. They set the tone, signaling its importance to the organization. Supervisor support provide guidance, direction, and help employees understand the change.
- That stress management is crucial during organizational change because change often causes stress and anxiety among employees. Self-management during organizational change is highly important because organizational change often requires individuals to adapt to new roles, processes, and ways of working. Time management of the rank-and-file employees during organizational change is effective. The employees can manage whatever changes they encounter in their work.
- That while the attitude of top management generally has a significant impact on employee management, there may be situations where it does not directly affect these aspects for rank-and-file employees. While the attitude of top management is generally considered influential, it is essential to recognize that its impact on specific aspects of employee management may vary depending on the organizational context, work structures, middle management influence, and individual employee characteristics. It is a complex interplay of various factors that collectively shape Employee experiences and outcomes.
- That the action plan is necessary to adapt to organizational change to improve work-life balance of rank-and-file employees.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the study recommends the following:

- Organizations and HR management communication may opt to use programs such as town halls to disseminate information to rank-and-file employees. Implementation in businesses would reap numerous benefits.
- Organizations and/or HR Management may opt to use additional wellness programs such as training, company events, mental health awareness, educational assistance, or reimbursement for Rank-and-File Employees. This would reap numerous benefits.
- Supervisory leadership may also be developed through training, which can be done in-house or outside the company. Supervisors can access available training online (e.g., Dale Carnegie's inspired executive leadership training, Global Knowledge, Mind Tools, MIT Open Courseware, Open Learn, and Skills Soft), and implementation in businesses would reap numerous benefits.

- Manufacturing companies may consider the action plan recommended to provide better communication for future organizational change and manage rank-and-file employees' work-life balance.
- Further researchers may investigate on the extent of challenges encountered in implementation of organizational change in other industries aside from the manufacturing industry to fully understand the relationship between organizational change and employees' work-life balance and the extent of the challenges associated with its implementation.

2. Literature review

Organizational change is a rapidly evolving process that requires organizations to adapt their operations, technologies, structures, and strategies. Effective change management is crucial for business success, and the Organizational Change Questionnaire—Climate Change, Process, and Readiness, Enamoring[45] assesses the readiness and effectiveness of organizations in implementing climate change-related initiatives.

Communication is essential for businesses to succeed, with HR groups acting as change catalysts and monitoring policies to maintain the desired culture. Employee involvement is a proven method for overcoming opposition to organizational change, and perceived social and organizational support, such as work relationships, information, and work-life balance, are positively related to positive attitudes toward change. Supervisors' support is also essential for learning motivation.

Work-life balance is vital for maintaining employee well-being and productivity, as it reduces stress levels, improves psychological well-being, and increases job satisfaction. Stress management strategies, such as time management, relaxation techniques, social support, and self-care, can help achieve work-life balance.

Organizations should address employee concerns and needs to mitigate negative impacts on work-life balance and help employees navigate the transition more effectively. Effective stress management can reduce stress, improve relationships, relaxation, enjoyment, and adaptability, allowing employees to persevere under stress and face obstacles head-on. Time management involves structuring the work schedule to meet goals set before them, and organizational readiness has a significant relationship with work-life balance.

3. Research method

Data were collected from Rank-and-File Employees of ABC Semiconductor Company since they represented the 80% of the company's population. they have a direct concern on organizational change and their Work-Life Balance. This company is located at Laguna Techno Park – Special Economic Zone, 4024 Biñan, Laguna. Philippines.

This study used a stratified random sampling method with G*power in determining the number of respondents that would be involved in this research. This method helps the researcher to divide the subjects into subgroups called strata based on characteristics that they shared then randomly sampled. In this research, the respondents were the Rank-and-File Employees since they represent 80% of the company's population and they have direct concern on organizational change and their Work-Life Balance, CFI Team [29].

The respondents to the study were the 200 Rank-and-File Employees since they represent 80% of the company's population and they have direct concern for organizational change and their Work-Life Balance. The Employees are categorized as Manufacturing Operators, Technicians and QA inspectors, and specialists whose interest was in organizational change and Work-Life balance.

Table 1 Respondents of the Study

End-Users	Total Population	Number of Respondents
Manufacturing Operator	110	35
Technicians	40	8
QA Inspector	30	8
Total	180	51

Table 1 shows the respondents of the study. It shows the total population of ABC Semiconductor Company of 180 Rank and File employees and 51 of them responded. The manufacturing operators had the highest response rate with 35 out of 110 responding. The technicians and QA inspectors had a lower response rate with eight out of 40 and eight out of 30 responded, respectively.

4. Findings and discussion

Results should be clear and concise. The results should summarize (scientific) findings rather than providing data in great detail. Please highlight differences between your results or findings and the previous publications by other researchers.

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- That the action plan is necessary to adapt to organizational change to improve work-life balance of rank-and-file employees.

5.1. Limitation and further research

This article explored the relationship between organizational change and employees' work-life balance in ABC Semiconductor Company, a prominent semiconductor company located in LTAI Biñan City, Laguna. The study aimed to analyze the impact of organizational change on employees' work-life balance and identify the factors that influence this relationship.

Compliance with ethical standards

Statement of informed consent

The participants were clearly informed that their involvement in the study was entirely voluntary, with the assurance that opting out would not impact their relationship with the researchers or the institution. Additionally, they were provided with detailed explanations regarding the confidentiality measures in place, including how their data would be anonymized, securely stored, and utilized solely for research purposes. The researcher diligently addressed all queries raised by the participants, ensuring thorough comprehension, and allowing ample time for deliberation. Prior to initiating any study-related procedures, each participant furnished written consent. It is imperative for me to adhere to ethical principles, meticulously document informed consent, and comply with pertinent laws governing research involving human subjects.

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Author's Short Biography

Mark Joseph Reolada Clarito is a seasoned Engineering Professional with a wealth of experience in the field. Currently serving as the Equipment Engineering Manager at PSI Technologies Inc., he brings a strong background in electrical engineering and business administration to his role.

Mark earned his Bachelor of Science degree majoring in Electrical Engineering from Colegio de San Juan de Letran in Calamba, Laguna. Building upon this foundation, he furthered his education by completing a Master's in Business Administration at Laguna College of Business and Art, also located in Calamba, Laguna.

With a diverse educational background and extensive experience in engineering management, **Mark** continues to make significant contributions to the industry while nurturing future talent in the field of engineering.